

FACTORS INFLUENCING PARENT'S VIEW ON PRESCHOOLS' ADVANCED LEARNING IN VARIOUS INTEREST CLASSES

DOI

Zhu Siyi

STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-5051-2831>

Mylene A. Bautista

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6801-8215>

Glyza B. Las Piñas

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9710-6037>

Dr. Jose M. Mongcal

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9135-3937>

Desirie Joy E. Laureta

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6015-3295>

Francisco E. Gedorio Jr.

Faculty, STI West Negros University, Bacolod City, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-5021-9657>

Abstract:

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes regarding academic performance, child's social development, health, and wellness, and economic factors. Moreover, this study aimed to find out whether or not significant differences exist in the following areas when the respondents are grouped and compared according to variables of age, sex, and average monthly family income. This study used descriptive research design to obtain information concerning the different areas cited and to describe what exists concerning other variables identified herein. Results show that the degree of influence of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes according to academic performance, child's social development, and health and wellness, all results are "high level" and for the economic factors is "very high level". Comparative analysis revealed that there is no significant difference in the degree of influence of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables except for the variable of sex in the area of economic factor which is "significant."

Keywords: Factors influencing parent's view, preschools' advanced learning, various interest classes, academic performance, child's social development, health and wellness, economic factors.

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

In today's early childhood education, parents have a widespread anxiety and comparison mentality about their children's education and underdevelopment. This psychological state of parents often manifests itself in their attention to the academic content of children. They unilaterally understand the connection of education as just the connection of content, hoping to enable children to access higher education content as soon as possible, believing that the sooner they learn, the better, "The earlier you learn, the stronger your knowledge will be, and it will enable your child to achieve the so-called" winning at the starting line. "However, such behavior of helping others grow up too early violates the laws of education and children's intellectual development." (Li Yanli, 2023)

Today, this phenomenon not only exists in extracurricular private educational institutions but also has a growing trend in some private and public kindergarten education. Most elementary school-level introductory courses are offered under the name of the preschool connection. For example, a bilingual kindergarten in Beijing has opened

more than ten courses, including Cambridge Children's English, Pinyin Literacy, Super Mental Arithmetic, and preschool connection. This "primary schooling" phenomenon in early childhood education will not help children transition smoothly between early childhood and early childhood. However, it will negatively impact and hide hazards in their subsequent learning (Li Yanli, 2023).

Children in the large kindergarten class are about to enter primary school and face a series of challenges, such as changes in learning styles, changes in the environment, and so on. Children who have not done an excellent job in connecting may experience many discomfort situations. As a mother of two and an administrator in an educational institution, the researcher observed that more and more parents came to consult with their children who wanted to learn subject knowledge before they went to school. They were afraid that their children would lose at the starting line. Although many children did not have heavy Academic burdens, parents arranged many extracurricular classes during break time, including Chinese, Mathematics, and English, as well as various interest classes. It is not ruled out that some children are interested, but parents impose most. Thus, the researcher wanted to determine different factors influencing parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes.

Current State of Knowledge

Childhood is a delicate, formative time in a person's life, and the socio-economic condition of their parents can have negative, long-lasting impacts on their health and well-being. Children have the right to participate in decisions that affect their lives, even while their parents' choices about family health affairs will impact their health and well-being. Health habits, such as physical activity and nutrition, can be viewed as part of a child's overall well-being as a multidimensional construct with mental, bodily, and social dimensions (Skogberg et al., 2022).

Kindergarten and primary school is the connection between kindergarten and primary school education. It is also a significant turning point that young children face in their development process. If handled properly, it will help their future development. The core is how young children of this age can effectively adapt to primary school life regarding thinking patterns, learning habits, and social skills and smoothly transition between young and primary school. Children in kindergarten and primary school have different physical and mental development characteristics. Solving the problem of linking early childhood education and primary education is of great significance for promoting sustainable human development and improving the quality of education (Xu Shumin, 2023).

The turnover rate of large-class children in kindergartens is increasing, mainly due to some parents sending large-class children to preschool classes run by some social institutions to receive preschool education. According to relevant national regulations, preschool education focuses on game teaching, and classes can be appropriately used. The upper limit of class hours per class and the number of class hours per week are strictly stipulated. At the same time, it is required that preschool children should not be allowed to learn first-grade textbooks, nor should homework or exams be reserved for them. However, many preschool classes must comply with relevant requirements, and preschool education has become a replica of primary school first-grade education. This way of connecting young children with young children violates the laws of their physical and psychological development. It can easily cause adverse effects on their physical and mental health development (Li Yanli, 2023).

To promote health and well-being, professionals who work with young children in health and social care or educational settings are in a critical position. It is crucial to encourage a child's active engagement during interventions and to boost their knowledge, motivation, competence, and self-efficacy. Long-term effects on an individual's health and well-being may be significantly influenced by supporting their capacity to make health-promoting decisions in their own lives (Mackiewicz et al., 2022).

While older children can easily focus on the assessment, younger children quickly get distracted, bored, or tired. Assessments may be unreliable with young children, so scores should be interpreted accordingly. A child who scores poorly on an estimate might have been bored, distracted, or confused by the task they are being asked to perform. The same child taking the same assessment another day may perform quite well. Data from any evaluation is valuable, but teachers should remember that it is just one source. Repeated formal and informal assessments will help establish a more valid and complete profile of the child's literacy knowledge and skills. Young children entering school should be given a screening assessment to determine if they are at risk of reading difficulties, and student progress should be monitored regularly. Beyond the preschool years, learning via play has become recognized as a crucial technique for fostering student engagement, inclusivity, and the development of all their talents. Policy, researchers, and educators view learning via play as developmentally appropriate because it taps into school-age children's natural curiosity while easing the frequently difficult transition from preschool to school. However, there needs to be more information on how learning via play can be used successfully in the formal educational setting and the factors that promote success (Parker, R., Thomsen, B., & Berry, A. J., 2022).

Preschool years are when children's formative development is most important. The fundamental building blocks of learning, cognitive development, academic success, information processing, language, and interpersonal skills are

gained and developed during a child's formative years. Given the growing body of evidence showing a connection between early life experiences and later adult health, preschools are well adapted to influencing children's general health and well-being. The learning opportunities provided by preschool and a good daycare for kids are abundant and have significant, long-lasting consequences. A thorough preschool evaluation covers all facets of the young child, enabling early detection of possible issues and the development of evidence-based therapies to address developmental deficiencies. The purpose of the preschool assessment will be explained in the following chapter, along with specific domains that should be taken into account and the systematic linking of proven interventions to support children's intellectual functioning, academic success, information processing, and skill development (Bracken et al.; L. A., 2023).

According to Paulson (2021), as government-funded preschool programs have expanded, their enrollment has also increased, reaching enrollment rates of 47 percent for four-year-olds and 16 percent for three-year-olds in 2019-2020. At that time, 37 percent of four-year-olds and 6 percent of three-year-olds were enrolled in state or locally-funded preschools. Another 7 percent of three and four-year-olds were enrolled in Head Start, a federally funded preschool program targeted for low-income families at or below 100 percent of the federal poverty line, and 3 percent were enrolled in special education. Newly enrolled preschoolers joining a universal public preschool program come from households that do not currently send these children to preschool and from households that switch from private to public preschool. While those young children who previously were not enrolled in any preschool receive a labor productivity boost from preschool education, children in households who switch from private to public preschool do not. These switching households effectively receive an increase to their household budget because their previous expense for private preschool is no longer necessary with the provision of the public program.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on the kindergarten theory of Dr. Maria Montessori (1907). According to this theory, children have a natural curiosity for learning and can take the initiative to start learning in a supportive, mindfully created learning environment. It is a strategy that honors the human spirit and a child's complete development, including physical, social, emotional, and cognitive growth (AMI, 2011).

Those Montessori principles are independence, observation, following the child, correcting the child, a prepared environment, and an absorbent mind. These concepts explain why things are such in a Montessori environment. Maria Montessori held these goals and beliefs regarding her education theory for children.

These are the contents of the Montessori theory: (1) Allow a child some independence. This theory says, "Never assist a child with a task that he feels he can complete on his own"; (2) observe the child by spending countless hours observing the child exploring his environment and enjoying what he does. For example, if a child starts banging on objects, it means that he needs that gross motor activity, so give him a drum; (3) Follow the child; they will demonstrate what they must do, what they must grow into, and what area they must be challenged in; (4) Correcting the child as he makes mistakes. He may spill something, drop food unintentionally, and so on. There is no need to raise your voice in situations like those. Instead, calmly recognize the mistake, "oh, you have spilled the water; why don't we get a cloth and wipe it up." This is an opportunity to ask the child to do some valid practical work with you; (5) regarding the prepared environment, this theory says, "Environment management is the teacher's first responsibility and takes precedence over all others. Although it has an indirect effect unless it is done effectively, there will not be any tangible, long-lasting benefits of any type, whether physical, intellectual, or spiritual"; and lastly (6) allow an absorbent mind. The language of the adult is one that a child will quickly pick up. Be careful of what you say around them. Even though you think they are not listening, as they may not be able to express themselves yet, you will not want them swearing back at you when they can.

The foundation of Montessori education is a model of human development and an educational strategy built on that model. There are two central tenets of the model. First, children and developing adults engage in psychological self-construction by interacting with their circumstances. Second, there is an innate psychological development path for youngsters, especially those under six. Based on her observations, Montessori theorized that kids who are allowed to make their own decisions and take their own actions in a setting designed according to her model will behave naturally for the best possible growth.

With the aid of Montessori's kindergarten theory as a guide, this research study will explore various areas of early childhood education in Jiaxing Qing'an International Bilingual Kindergarten in Jiaxing City.

Objectives

This study aimed to determine the factors influencing parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in some Kindergarten Schools in Jiaxing City. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions: 1) the profile of the respondents in terms of variable of age, sex and average monthly family income; 2)

degree of (influence) of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes according to the area of academic performance, child's social development, health and wellness, economic factors; and 3) the significant difference in the degree of influence of factors influencing parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Methodology

This section presents a discussion of the research methodology used, the subjects and respondents of the study, the research instruments used, the validity and reliability of the instruments, the procedure for data gathering, and the statistical tools and procedures for data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed descriptive research design to determine the factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. According to Bueno (2016) descriptive research design describe systematically the facts and characteristics of a given population or area of interest factually and accurately. In this investigation, the focus was on the degree of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. Descriptive research will be used to obtain information concerning on academic performance, parent's perception, child's social development and health and wellness to describe what exists with respect to different variables identified herein.

Study Respondents

This study selected the 92 parents of large class children who are most closely related to the connection between kindergarten and primary school as the research object. Therefore, the term "parents of young children" in this article refers to parents of preschool children aged 5 to 6 years.

Instruments

The study used a self-made survey questionnaire. It was subjected to validity (4.92-excellent) and reliability (0.939-excellent). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good; respectively. This study used a self-made questionnaire in gathering all the necessary data. The questionnaire consists of two parts: Part 1 contains queries on respondents' profile such age, sex, and average monthly family income; and Part 2 is the questionnaire proper that deals on the factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. The respondents were asked to rate each item using the five point Likert's scale which contained the following scores: 5 (Very High), 4 (High), 3 (Moderate), 2 (Low), 1 (Very Low).

Data Gathering Procedure

In gathering the data, the researcher seeks permission from the school administrator. Upon approval, the researcher also seeks permission from the respondents to participate in the study before administering the instrument. After establishing contact with the respondents, the researcher explains the study's purpose, which will determine the factors influencing parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. The terms of confidentiality and anonymity of the gathered data will be emphasized. After answering the survey, the questionnaires were immediately retrieved, and the data were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted by the researcher to suffice the problem with answers and to come up with a valid conclusion.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 employs the descriptive-analytical scheme and frequency and percentage distributions to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of sex, highest educational attainment, and average monthly family income.

Objective No. 2 employs the descriptive-analytical scheme and mean to determine the degree of influence of factors influencing parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes according to the areas of academic performance, personal perception, child's social development, health, and wellness.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative-analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine the significant differences in the degree of influence of factors influencing parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables.

Ethical Consideration

Informed consent via verbal communication was elicited with the respondents. They read and understood the provided information and can ask questions. Moreover, their participation was voluntary, and they were free to withdraw without giving any reasons. The respondents were assured that there would be no risks of harm will experience before, during, or after participating in the research. The researcher assures the respondents' confidentiality and anonymity, including their personal information.

Results and Discussion

This section presents, analyzes, and interprets the data that were gathered consistent with its predetermined objectives.

Table 1
Profile of the Respondents

Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	Younger (below 34 years old)	36	39.1
	Older (34 years old & above)	56	60.9
Sex	Male	38	41.3
	Female	54	58.7
Average Monthly Income	Family Lower (below RMB 8,000)	25	27.2
	Higher (RMB 8,000 & above)	67	72.8
Total		92	100.00

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of ninety-two (92) parents regarding their age, sex, and average family monthly income in tabular form.

The respondents comprised 36 younger parents, 39.1%, and 56 older parents, or 60.9% of the total population. Meanwhile, 41.3% of the respondents are male, and 58.7% are female. And regarding average family monthly income, 27.2% have a lower income, and 72.8% have a higher income.

Table 2
Level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area academic performance

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I encourage my child to do his homework independently but give necessary help when needed.	4.35	High Degree
2. I usually observe the child's ability to master the correct sitting and pen-holding posture.	4.10	High Degree
3. I often consciously introduce the learning and life situation of primary school to children	3.11	Moderate Degree
4. I focus on cultivating children's interest in learning	3.94	High Degree
5. I usually pay great attention to the child's focus on completing everything	3.89	High Degree
6. I often read stories to my children or read with them	4.26	High Degree
7. I often teach children some common knowledge about life and nature	4.30	High Degree
Mean	3.99	High Degree

Results show an overall mean of 3.99 which interpreted as high Degree. Among the seven items, item no. 1 "I encourage my child to do his homework independently but give necessary help when needed" got the highest mean of 4.35 which interpreted as high level while item no. 3 "I often consciously introduce the learning and life situation of primary school to children" got the lowest mean of 3.11 which interpreted as moderate level. This implies that parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in terms of academic performance is more on the introduction of real life situation's learning and have their children be prepared of what is needed as they grow up which according to Munday 2016, success in school in the early grades is vitally important. It is known that children who get off to a good start rarely struggle, while those who fall behind tend to stay behind throughout their school years. This connotes that both studies believe on very good early education will helps prepare these young children for their future.

Table 3
Level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area child social development

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I allow my child to play and mingle with other children.	3.77	High Degree
2. I attach great importance to cultivating the interaction between children, teachers, and adults	3.67	High Degree

3. I attach great importance to cultivating civilized and polite behavior in children's interactions with others	4.50	Very High Degree
4. I attach great importance to letting children do what they can	4.26	High Degree
5. I attach great importance to cultivating children's ability to do things according to requirements	3.94	High Degree
6. I allow the developing children's cognitive abilities towards themselves, others, and interpersonal relationships	4.05	High Degree
7. I cultivate the formation and development of children's communication skills	4.41	High Degree
Mean	4.08	High Degree

Table 3 revealed results on parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in child social development. The overall mean is 4.08 which interpreted as high degree where item no 3 "I attach great importance to cultivating civilized and polite behavior in children's interactions with others" got the highest mean of 4.50 which interpreted as very high degree. The rest of the items got an interpretation of high degree but item no. 2 "I attach great importance to cultivating the interaction between children, teachers, and adults" got the lowest mean among them. This implies that parents are more concerned with how their children interact with other children, teachers and adults. How these children behave nowadays is very common due to children are more inclined with their gadgets and does online games in the online world and social interaction with others were disregarded.

This is also aligned to the study of Parker, R., Thomsen, B., & Berry, A. J., 2022 entitled Learning through Play at School – A Framework for Policy and Practice, stated "Learning through play has emerged as an important strategy to promote student engagement, inclusion, and holistic skills development beyond the preschool years. Policy makers, researchers and educators have promoted the notion that learning through play is developmentally appropriate—as it leverages school-age children's innate curiosity while easing the often difficult transition from preschool to school. However, there is a dearth of evidence and practical guidance on how learning through play can be employed effectively in the formal school context and the conditions that support success".

Table 4

Level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area health and wellness

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I ensure my child is in good condition before going to school.	4.85	Very High Degree
2. I attach great importance to developing children's sports, including major ones.	4.27	High Degree
3. I attach great importance to developing fine motor skills in young children.	4.13	High Degree
4. I consider children's differentiated cognition of their gender roles.	4.44	High Degree
5. I look into the development of children's mental health	4.68	Very High Degree
6. I consider the psychological abilities of children in the process of interacting with peers	4.44	High Degree
7. I pay attention to the development and changes in children's social emotions	4.50	Very High Degree
Mean	4.47	High Degree

Results revealed that parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in health and wellness got the overall mean of 4.47, which was interpreted as high degree. Among the seven items, item no. 1 "I ensure my child is in good condition before going to school" got the highest mean score of 4.85 which interpreted as very high level while item no. 3 "I attach great importance to developing fine motor skills in young children" got the lowest mean score of 4.13 which interpreted as high degree. This implies that among these seven items parents has concerned with giving importance in developing the fine motors of their children where fine motor skills are activities in which you use the small muscles in your hands and wrists to make precise movements. In this area, parents are hoping with the help of teachers in school to have their children activities to develop their fine motor skills as supported by study of Mackiewicz, et.al. (2022) that Professionals working with young children in health and social care or educational settings are in a key position to promote health and wellbeing. Furthermore, supporting an individual's ability to make health-promoting decisions in their own life may have a significant influence on their overall health and wellbeing in the long term.

Table 5

Level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area economic factors

Items	Mean	Interpretation
1. I provided all the materials needed by my child in school.	4.72	Very High Degree

2. I prepare a suitable learning environment for my children	4.68	Very High Degree
3. I purchase necessary school supplies for the child	4.73	Very High Degree
4. I consider the cost of registering children for interest classes	4.42	High Degree
5. I check on the level of children's tuition fees	4.30	High Degree
6. I consider if there is diversity in children's interest classes	4.45	High Degree
7. I pay attention to children's secular education or spiritual education.	4.44	High Degree
Mean	4.54	Very High Degree

Regarding economic factors, the results show that parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes got the overall mean of 4.54 which interpreted as very high degree. Item no. 3 "I purchase necessary school supplies for the child" got the highest mean of 4.73 which interpreted as very high degree while item no.5 "I check on the level of children's tuition fees" got the lowest mean of 4.30 which interpreted as high degree. This implies that parents in choosing the school of their children they consider the tuition fees of each school. Anywhere in the world preschool tuition fees are a lot higher than the adult schools that is why parents need more budget to fund for their children's education. It is good if the government could provide financial assistance to these families as cited in the study of Paulson (2021) that newly enrolled preschoolers joining a universal public preschool program come both from households who do not currently send these children to preschool at all and from households who switch from private to public preschool. These switching households effectively receive an increase to their household budget because their previous expense for private preschool is no longer necessary with the provision of the public program.

Table 6

Difference in the level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area academic performance When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	36	46.32	1001.500	0.958	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	56	46.62				
Sex	Male	38	46.22	1015.500	0.933	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	54	46.69				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	25	50.90	727.500	0.331	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	67	44.86				

Results revealed that parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in academic performance When Grouped and Compared According to age, sex, and average family monthly income is insignificant. This implies that in terms of academic performance of these children, the parent's generation, whether young or old, male or female, with low or high income, does not affect their academic performance.

This result supports on the study of Bracken, B. A. and Theodore, L. A. (2023) that preschool and quality daycare provides rich opportunities for children's learning, yielding long-lasting and significant effects. Thus, young children academic performance does not depend on their parent's age, gender and income. Comprehensive preschool assessment sheds light on aspects of the whole child, providing early identification of potential problems and the subsequent development of evidence-based interventions to address delays in development

Table 7

Difference in the level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area child's social development when grouped and compared according to the aforementioned variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	36	46.36	1003.000	0.168	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	56	46.59				

Sex	Male	38	42.08	858.000	0.181	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	54	49.61				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	25	51.78	705.500	0.244	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	67	44.53				

Results show that parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the child's social development when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and average family monthly income is insignificant. This implies that in terms of the child's social development of these children's parent's generation, whether young or old, male or female, with low or high income, they have the same goal to have their children grown up with a healthy social interaction with other children and adults.

The results of this study would agree to what Vogglar, et.al. (2008) cited in their study that children face many important changes in the first eight years of life, including different learning centers, social groups, roles and expectations. Their ability to adapt to such a dynamic and evolving environment directly affects their sense of identity and status within their community over the short and long term.

Table 8

Difference in the level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area health and wellness When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	36	41.15	815.500	0.120	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	56	49.94				
Sex	Male	38	47.61	984.000	0.737	0.05	Not Significant
	Female	54	45.72				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	25	40.40	685.000	0.177	0.05	Not Significant
	Higher	67	48.78				

Table 8 results revealed that parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in health and wellness, when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and average family monthly income, is not significant. This implies that all parents prioritize their children's health and wellness. No parents wish to have their child get sick due to so many academic demands. Parents always want what is best for their children.

As emphasized in the study of Bracken, B. A. and Theodore, L. A. (2023). Children's formative development is most critical during the preschool years. It is during the earliest years of a child's life when the fundamental building blocks of learning, cognitive development, academic achievement, information processing, language, and interpersonal skills are acquired and developed. Comprehensive preschool assessment sheds light on aspects of the whole child, providing early identification of potential problems and the subsequent development of evidence-based interventions to address delays in development.

Table 9

Difference in the level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area Economic Factors When Grouped and Compared According to the Aforementioned Variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	36	43.63	904.500	0.403	0.05	Not Significant
	Older	56	48.35				
Sex	Male	38	60.57	491.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Female	54	36.60				
Average Family Monthly Income	Lower	25	39.82	670.500	0.138	0.05	Not Significant

Income	Higher	67	48.99
--------	--------	----	-------

Results show that parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in economic factors is not significant when grouped and compared according to age and average family monthly income. At the same time, in terms of sex, the result is substantial. This implies that parents' generation and average family monthly income do not affect how they view preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. They both believe that these children need to be educated at an early age, while in terms of sex, female parents have different views than male parents.

Moreover, in this study, among the three variables of gender, age, and average monthly household income, gender can become a factor that affects parents' choices for early childhood transition. The characteristic influence in the results means that there are differences in the thinking of men and women, and mothers are more inclined to establish a stable and good internal personality for their children during the transition, such as becoming kind, helpful, and outgoing. And fathers tend to encourage their children to learn a skill in the preschool transition class, such as learning swimming, martial arts, dance, and other abilities.

Conclusions

Given the above findings, the following conclusions were drawn: The majority of the respondents belong to the older group, females with a higher income.

In the area of academic performance, parent's view of preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in terms of academic performance is more on the introduction of real-life situations learning and have their children be prepared for what is needed as they grow up for success in school in the early grades is vitally important. It is known that children who get off to a good start rarely struggle, while those who fall behind tend to stay behind throughout their school years.

In the area of child social development, parents are more concerned with how their children interact with other children, teachers, and adults. How these children behave nowadays is very common due to children being more inclined to their gadgets and online games in the online world and social interaction with others were disregarded.

In the area of health and wellness, parents has concerned with giving importance to developing the fine motor of their children where fine motor skills are activities in which you use the small muscles in your hands and wrists to make precise movements. In this area, parents are hoping with the help of teachers in school to have their children's activities to develop their fine motor skills.

In the area of economic factors, parents in choosing the school of their children consider the tuition fees of each school. Anywhere in the world preschool tuition fees are a lot higher than the adult schools which is why parents need more budget to fund their children's education. It is good if the government could provide financial assistance to these families.

There is no significant difference in the level of factors influencing parents' view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area of academic performance, child's social development, health and wellness when grouped and compared according to age, sex, and average family monthly income.

There is no significant difference in the level of factors influencing parent's view on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes in the area of economic factors when grouped and compared according to age, and average family monthly income while in terms of sex, the result is significant.

According to the data from this study, economic factors can greatly influence parents' choices for early childhood transition. Because even if many parents want their children to participate in early childhood transition learning, whether it is building internal character or cultivating external skills, they require a certain amount of financial investment, which means that the family needs to have a long-term and stable economic foundation. Without this basic condition, even if parents have strong ideas, they cannot choose the corresponding preschool transition.

Recommendations

Considering these findings and conclusions, the researcher as a result of this offers the following recommendations:

Government Departments:

The main reason for the high price of connecting young and primary schools is that the vast majority of institutions are private enterprises, whose fundamental purpose is to make profits, which will increase the price of tuition fees. So if the national government can support existing public kindergartens to spontaneously carry out early childhood transition courses, based on the vast majority of family conditions, then the price set is fair and can be accepted by everyone. Therefore, early childhood transition can be carried out orderly and quickly with the support of the government.

Schools Administrator:

Based on the results, school administrators implement intervention plans to strengthen parents' views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes. These intervention plans will deal with activities and programs that cater to young children's needs to prepare them for their future while enjoying their childhood years.

Curriculum Planners:

It is recommended to the curriculum planners formulate curriculum plans, and design courses of action that could serve as the basis for strengthening preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes.

Teachers:

Based on the results, it is recommended to the teachers give a fresh outlook in understanding the reasons for parent's different views on preschools' advanced learning in various interest classes.

Parents:

It is recommended the parents have a clearer view and encouragement to have their children engage in advanced learning in various interest classes. It is further recommended that parents choose to have children in a stable and high-income state to ensure a stable growth environment and economic foundation for their children.

Acknowledgment

The researcher would like to express her heartfelt gratitude to all people who extended their support, aided, and guided in completing this manuscript. To her adviser and panel members for their constant support, guidance, and conscientious efforts in making this dream come true, sharing their completion and success of the study. Thank you so much for your strong support and guidance. The researcher also thanks her parents for their care and support during her study period and the children who accompanied her for their tremendous support. Thank you to the kindergarten parents for their active cooperation, which enabled her to obtain more authentic and valuable data. Finally, the researcher would like to credit herself for this success and thank herself for continuously seek for progress and always trying to improve herself. She wants to be happy forever, become her best version, and never forget her original intention.

References

- Allan, Mark. (2013). Qualitative Study of Kindergarten School Readiness and Personal and Social Development. Dissertation submitted to the faculty of Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy. Educational Leadership and Policy Studies.
- Bracken, B. A. and Theodore, L. A. (2023) "Promoting Health and Wellness in Young Children: Preschool Assessment," Perspectives on Early Childhood Psychology and Education: Vol. 5: Iss. 1, Article 7. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.58948/2834-8257.1046>
- Doskocil, Dayna. (2016). The 3 main challenges teachers face in today's classroom. Classroom Craft. Retrieved online on March 1, 2019 from <https://www.classcraft.com/blog/features/3-main-challenges-teachers-face/>
- Fulgencio, R. G., & Maguate, G. (2023). Awareness and Implementation of the Public Elementary School Teachers of the Positive Discipline Model: Basis for a Guidance program. International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS), 6(08), 41-61.
- Jayne, R., & Maguate, G. (2023). Issues and Concerns of Teachers towards Modular Distance Learning Approach. International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM), 11(08), 2848-2857.
- Krugman, P. (2023). *Economic Factors: How Economic Factors Affect Businesses - 2023 - MasterClass*. <https://www.masterclass.com/articles/economic-factors>
- Maguate, G. S., & Rabacal, J. S. (2023). Peer Mentoring for Academic Performance of Students in science. International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS), 6(06), 183-189.
- Munday, Amanda. (2016). 7 Common Challenges Faced by Preschool Teachers. Early Childhood Education Blog by Himana.com. Retrieved online on February 24, 2019 from <https://blog.himama.com/7-challenges-of-being-a-preschool-teacher/>

- Mendoza, M. C., Geroso, M. J., & Maguate, G. S. (2023). Hearing the Unheard: Unveiling the Untold Stories of Hearing-Impaired Students in Inclusive Education. *International Journal of Latest Research in Humanities and Social Science (IJLRHSS)*, 6(8), 01-09.
- Orillosa, Joyce Ferro and Magno, Carlo. (2013). Parental Involvement in Children's Assessment in Kindergarten. *Educational Measurement and Evaluation Review, De La Salle University*. (2013), Vol. 4, 47-65.
- Parker, R., Thomsen, B., & Berry, A. J. (2022). Learning Through Play at School – A Framework for Policy and Practice. *Frontiers in Education*, 7. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2022.751801>
- Pasique, D. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Challenges And Opportunites Among Educators in The Implementation of Continuing Professional Development. *International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research (IJFMR)*, 5(4).
- Paulson, M. (2021). Economic Effects from Preschool and Childcare Programs — Penn Wharton Budget Model. Penn Wharton Budget Model. <https://budgetmodel.wharton.upenn.edu/issues/2021/8/23/economic-effects-preschool-and-childcare-programs>
- Pearson, T., Wagner, S. L., & Schmidt, G. M. (2020). Parental perspective: Factors that played a role in facilitating or impeding the parents' understanding of their child's developmental diagnostic assessment. *Child Care Health and Development*. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cch.12751>
- Rheinschmidt, M. L., & Mendoza-Denton, R. (2014). Social class and academic achievement in college: The interplay of rejection sensitivity and entity beliefs. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 107(1), 101–121. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0036553>
- Rozek, C. S., Ramirez, G., Fine, R., & Beilock, S. L. (2019). Reducing socioeconomic disparities in the STEM pipeline through student emotion regulation. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 116(5), 1553–1558. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1808589116>
- Salutin, M. A., & Maguate, G. (2023). Values-Based Exercises for the Development of Reading Readiness Skills for Preschool Children. *International Journal of Scientific Research and Management (IJSRM)*, 11(08), 22-30.
- Sapungan, Gina & Sapungan, Ronel. (2014). Parental Involvement in Child's Education: Importance, Barriers and Benefits. *Asian Journal of Management Sciences & Education* Vol. 3(2).
- Skogberg, M., Mackiewicz, K., Mänd, K., Tuuling, L., Urdzina-Merca, I., Salanterä, S., & Pakarinen, A. (2022). Promoting the health and wellbeing of children: A feasibility study of a digital tool among professionals. *PLOS ONE*, 17(3), e0265355. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0265355>
- Sotto, N. A. B., Geroso, M. J. S., Hofileña, H. S., Geroso, P. J. M. S., & Maguate, G. S. (2023). GAMES: Gamification and Mathematics Education synergy. *International Journal of applied Science and Technology (IJAST)*, 13(02), 41-48.
- Vogler, P., Crivello, G. and Woodhead, M. (2008) Early childhood transitions research: A review of concepts, theory, and practice. Working Paper No. 48. The Hague, The Netherlands: Bernard van Leer Foundation.